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**DRAFT - CONP Publication
Policy**

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This Policy is Still Under Development – The CONP Publication Policy is still under development and may change depending on feedback from stakeholders. This document should be thought of as a preprint draft to enable community engagement and input.

The CONP Portal Terms of Use, CONP Portal Contributor Agreement, and the various pages referred to within this document are also still under development. They will be shared with the community for comment as initial versions become ready for release. As such most blue-underlined text are not hyperlinks but indicate where hyperlinks will be.

We welcome all input on the contents of this document. Any feedback or questions can be sent to Dylan Roskams-Edris at dylan.roskamsedris@gmail.com. Please respond with feedback by August 17th, 2019 and include your name and relationship to the CONP community in your email.

CONP Publication Policy

Preamble

To meet the goals of open science and respect the dual human rights of everyone to benefit from scientific advancements and of scientists to be recognized for their contributions (*Universal Declaration of Human Rights*, art.27), this Publication Policy provides guidance for building an innovative, open platform to accelerate discovery and promote health benefits. This Publication Policy should be read with reference to both CONP's mission and its *Ethics and Data Governance Framework*.

1.0 Publication Policy Background

1.1 The Canadian Open Neuroscience Platform (CONP) believes that sharing scientific resources - including data, software, protocols, and papers - as widely and as openly as possible will increase the quality of science and the number of scientific discoveries. To demonstrate its commitment to this belief the CONP has developed a Publication Policy to encourage and enable researchers to share their research resources widely and openly.

1.2 This policy document explains of how the CONP helps foster collaboration in a complex distributed research setting. The primary approach is to encourage open science by identifying best practices and providing relevant and easily digestible information to users. The [CONP Portal Terms of Use](#) and [CONP Portal Contributor Agreement](#) apply conditions on how certain resources can be shared and used to ensure that what users find on the CONP Portal is as openly accessible and useable as possible. The conditions relate to citation practices and limiting the restrictions imposed by intellectual property. Any conditions on use are directly posted or linked to on every resource landing page.

2.0 Open Access Publishing

2.1 **Background Information** - Scholarly articles published in scientific journals are the main way researchers share their results with the scientific community. A key component open science is making sure that barriers to accessing and using the content of these publications are reduced or eliminated. Publishing in an open access journal ensures that articles can be freely accessed, shared, used, and adapted.

2.2 **Rationale** - The elimination of access and use restrictions enabled by open access publishing increases the ability of researchers to engage with and replicate one another's work. It also serves the public by allowing interested citizens to stay involved with scientific developments.

2.3 **Open Access Publishing of Papers Generated Using Shared Resources** - The CONP strongly encourages users to publish any articles based on resources shared through the CONP Portal in an open access journal that makes published articles immediately and freely available.

2.4 **Additional Information** - To help researchers publish openly the CONP has collected information about open access requirements of funders and institutions, open access policies of journals, and how open access

publishing costs can be offset. This information can be accessed on the CONP's [Open Access Publishing Information](#) page.

3.0 Preprints and Postprints

3.1 Background Information - Another important way of making publications openly accessible is by depositing copies of articles submitted to journals in openly accessible repositories. The version of an article an author can deposit varies between journals. Some journals allow authors to submit the final published version (a “postprint”) while others only allow an earlier non-final version (a “preprint”), while others require the author to hold off on depositing copies during an embargo period.

3.2 Rationale - Submitting preprints and postprints plays a key role in opening science. If the journal that accepts an article is closed access then the deposited copy makes the results the publication communicates openly accessible. A parallel copy in a repository also means that even if the journal were to cease to exist or have its data deleted a copy would remain findable and accessible.

3.3 CONP Policy - The CONP [strongly encourages](#) users who have submitted articles based on resources shared through the CONP Portal to deposit preprints and/or postprints of those articles in appropriate openly accessible repositories.

3.4 Additional Information - Information concerning appropriate repositories, as well as resources to help users find journal policies concerning depositing copies of articles, can be found on the CONP's [Open Access Publishing Information](#) page.

4.0 Citing Resources Shared Through the CONP Portal

4.1 Background Information - One result of open science will be that scholarly articles, research proposals, abstracts submitted to conferences, posters, and conference presentations may be based on the work of researchers distributed across different research environments. Data and software shared through the CONP Portal and used to generate research outputs may be created by multiple researchers distributed among distinct institutions.

4.2 Rationale - Sharing credit in a fair and transparent way through citation using persistent digital identifiers will help encourage continued sharing of resources through the CONP Portal as well as creating the links between data, software, physical materials, methods, and results necessary for open and replicable science. Applying minimally-restrictive citation conditions to certain resources shared through the CONP Portal helps ensure these goals are met.

4.3 Citation Using Resource DOI and Resource Specific Citation Preference - The CONP supports fair citation practices in two ways: (1) by providing a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) for each resource shared through the CONP, and (2) enabling those who share resources to specify how they would like to be cited by supplying a resource specific citation preference. As reflected in the [CONP Portal Terms of Use](#), users must use the DOI

and any resource specific citation preference in the citation section or main body of any paper, poster, presentation, or other publicly disclosed research output that relies on a resource shared through the CONP Portal.

4.4 **Additional Information** - Information explaining how to find a resource's DOI and a resource's specific citation preference, and guidance on how to cite within different research outputs, can be found on the CONP's [Information on Sharing Resources Through the CONP](#) page.

5.0 Open Sharing of Modified Data

5.1 **Background Information** - Openly shared data will often only be the starting point of further research. Upon accessing data a researcher may process, transform, combine, or modify it to fit the needs of their research. These modified datasets, and the software used to modify them, are important resources that may enable further work and, especially if used for publication purposes, should be re-shared with the scientific community.

5.2 **Rationale** - The CONP wants to support a sustainable and growing open data environment. An important part of this goal is for modified data to be reshared, described, and linked to the original data. Doing so will allow CONP users to rapidly build on and contribute to each other's work.

5.3 **Resharing Modified Data** - The CONP strongly encourages its users to re-share any data that has been modified from data originally accessed through CONP Portal. Re-sharing is especially important if the modified data was used to generate a publication or other publicly disclosed research output. The re-shared data should be clearly linked to the original data by using the original data's DOI and any resource specific citation preference.

5.4 **Resharing Software Used to Modify Data** - If software was used to modify re-shared data the user should describe the software used in the re-shared data's description and, if possible, include a link to an openly accessible software repository where a copy of the software has been made available.

5.5 **Additional Information** - For more information on modified of datasets and sharing data through the CONP Portal please visit the CONP's [Information on Sharing Resources Through the CONP](#) page.

6.0 Open Sharing of Modified Software

6.1 **Background Information** - Software for collecting, processing, modeling, and visualizing data is becoming an ever more important part of science. When such software is openly shared it can be accessed and modified to fit the needs of a specific research context, further accelerating discovery. Re-sharing modified software is important for both allowing others to build on that work as well as replicating reported results. The CONP employs software pipelines that allow users to apply software shared on other platforms to data shared through the CONP Portal, and will provide a method for accessing that software either by providing a link to where that software is shared or by allowing users to download it directly.

6.2 Rationale - In addition to supporting a sustainable and growing open data environment the CONP wants to support sustainable and growing open software development. Re-sharing modified software is key to accomplishing this goal, enabling researchers to engage with one another's work, and making sure results are replicable.

6.3 Resharing Modified Software - The CONP strongly encourages its users to re-share any software that has been materially modified from software originally accessed through the CONP Portal. Re-sharing is especially important if the software was used to generate a publication or other publicly disclosed research output.

6.4 Users should share any modified versions of software through an openly accessible platform. Users should also document the modifications made and include the original software's DOI (or other persistent digital identifier) and any resource specific citation preference.

6.5 Additional Information - For more information on modification of software and sharing software please visit the CONP's [Information on Sharing Resources Through the CONP](#) page.